

CARBON SEQUESTRATION IN FLOODPLAIN FORESTS

TEACHING PROTOCOL

TYPE OF LESSON: STEM workshop

GRADE LEVEL: Secondary School

LESSON STRUCTURE: min. two school lessons for the introduction ("Engage"),
min. four school lessons for the field trip ("Explore")
min. four school lessons for background information on carbon sequestration, carbon calculation, and impacts of CO₂ ("Explain" & "Elaborate")

INTRODUCTION:

This learning unit aims to help students understand the importance of carbon sequestration in the tree biomass of healthy (wetland) forests. The students learn about the role of CO₂ as a greenhouse gas, and significant natural and human CO₂ sources and sinks. The activities highlight the crucial role of forests in sequestering carbon, thereby mitigating climate change and preserving natural nutrient cycles. Students integrate theoretical information with their field experience to form a comprehensive understanding of the carbon cycle. They are encouraged to critically evaluate questions concerning land-use and its potential impact on carbon sequestration, as well as the factors that may influence carbon sequestration in various (wetland) forests.

The school lessons presented here are part of the Horizon Europe project Restore4Life and primarily focus on wetland forests. However, they can be adapted for use in any forest setting. Additionally, the lesson can be expanded to include investigations of soil organic carbon (see "Carbon sequestration and storage in soils").

LEARNING OBJECTIVES:

By the end of this lesson, students will be able to:

- 1 Identify key carbon sinks and sources in wetlands
- 2 Estimate the carbon sequestration potential of different wetland areas
- 3 Calculate above- and below-ground carbon stores in tree biomass
- 4 Understand the role of wetlands in controlling and reducing global warming
- 5 Assess human impacts on wetlands' carbon sequestration potential

KEYWORDS: Carbon sequestration, carbon sink/source, above-ground and below-ground biomass, greenhouse gases, warming potential

TEACHING FRAMEWORK BASED ON THE 5E INSTRUCTIONAL MODEL

1. ENGAGE - Sparking curiosity

AIM: Students can explain how greenhouse gases contribute to global warming and how CO₂ in the atmosphere is removed by carbon sequestration (i.e., the incorporation of CO₂ into plant biomass via primary production). They can name important carbon sinks (e.g., forests, peatlands) and sources (e.g., anoxic sediments of water bodies) in wetlands and other ecosystems.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- How do water vapor, CO₂, and other greenhouse gases (e.g., methane) cause global warming? What are the main sources for these gases?
- How is CO₂ naturally removed from the atmosphere? What does carbon sequestration mean? Why are intact (wetland) forests important for carbon sequestration?
- Which conditions in wetlands favor carbon sinks and sources?

TEACHER SUPPORT: The activity is split into two tasks: (1) A short indoor experiment to demonstrate the warming effects of CO₂ and water vapor on air temperature, and (2) an internet search.

(1) CLIMATE CHANGE EXPERIMENT

This activity helps students understand the concept of climate change by conducting a small-scale experiment on global warming in a classroom setting. Through this hands-on experiment, students will gain insight into the greenhouse effect and observe how different atmospheric conditions influence temperature changes.

ACTIVITY OVERVIEW: Students will set up three glass bottles, each representing different atmospheric conditions: a control bottle with normal air, a bottle with added water vapor, and a bottle with CO₂ generated from a reaction between limestone and a descaling solution. Infrared lamps will simulate solar radiation, and temperature changes will be recorded over time.

DISCUSSION POINTS: Before starting, discuss the greenhouse effect and its significance in climate change. Ask students to hypothesize which bottle will show the greatest temperature increase and why. After collecting data, facilitate a discussion on the results and their implications for understanding global warming.

EXPECTED RESULTS: The temperature in the water vapor bottle and the CO₂ bottle will rise faster and reach a higher end temperature than the reference bottle with just air. The CO₂ bottle will show a higher temperature increase than the water vapor bottle.

DETAILED INSTRUCTIONS: see worksheet "Engage"

(2) INTERNET SEARCH

This activity helps students develop research skills and deepen their understanding of climate change topics by conducting an internet search to gather and evaluate information. Through this exercise, students will learn about greenhouse gases, global warming, and carbon sequestration, and they will practice assessing the trustworthiness of online

ACTIVITY OVERVIEW:

1. Students are divided into small groups of 3-4 people. Half of the groups collect background information on greenhouse gases and global warming (how do greenhouse gases cause global warming? Which is the most potent greenhouse gas?). The other half focuses on carbon sequestration (What is it? Which natural habitats have the highest potential? Which have a low potential).
2. After 30 minutes, the students present their findings to the others.
3. The students draw a mind-map of the (global) carbon cycle.

DISCUSSION POINTS:

Discuss the importance of reliable sources and how to evaluate the trustworthiness of information found online. Encourage students to think critically about the sources they use and to cross-reference information. After the presentations, facilitate a discussion on the global carbon cycle and how the topics of greenhouse gases and carbon sequestration are interconnected

MATERIALS NEEDED:

Computer or smartphones; links to search for information; instructions on how to search and decide whether these are trustworthy resources

2. EXPLORE – Hands-on learning activity

AIM Students can measure and calculate the above- and below-ground organic carbon stored in tree biomass.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- How can you estimate the above-ground and below-ground organic carbon storage of trees in the field?
- Which habitat do you think has the highest biomass?

TEACHER SUPPORT:

This activity aims to provide students with practical experience in measuring and calculating the above- and below-ground organic carbon stored in tree biomass. By engaging in fieldwork, students will learn how to estimate carbon storage in different habitats and understand the ecological significance of tree biomass. They will need support from teachers in pre-selecting a survey area and sites within this survey area, as this makes it easier for students to focus on the measurement and data collection process. The activity involves using a smartphone app to identify tree species and recording data for further analysis.

MATERIALS NEEDED:

flexible 2 m tape, smartphone, stick of at least an arm's length

ACTIVITY OVERVIEW:

1. **Select a survey area:** Teachers select a survey area that is similar to one of the habitats from the internet research in task 1. If the tree density is low, estimating tree height is easier. Additionally, open spaces adjacent to the survey area, such as meadows, simplify the task.
2. **Select sites within the survey area:** Teachers select 3-5 easily accessible and representative sites within the survey area. Each site should have an area of approximately 20 m in length and 10 m in width. For tree height estimations, you must see the entire tree from approximately 20 m. Thus, in dense forests, select a site along a path.
3. **Form small groups:** Divide students into groups of 2-4 participants.
4. **Documentation of the process:** The students take a picture of each site and note the GPS data, the date, and time of the survey in the "Tree biomass" form (worksheet).
5. **Measurements and Calculations:** The students measure the circumference of each tree within this site via the "Diameter-at-Breast-Height method" (see worksheet), identify each tree species using the App "Flora incognita" and estimate the tree height via the "Triangle method" (see worksheet). With the mean height and the exact circumference, they can estimate the trees' biomass.
6. **Optional:** The students add indicator values for each species using the Flora incognita. Go to the species description and scroll down to "treat". Depending on the species, you can find information on the type of pollination, leaf endurance, toxicity, protection value, and indicator values for nutrients (nitrate), moisture, light, temperature, soil reaction (pH), and salinity. The indicators provide information about the ecological requirements of the species. The higher the value, the more the plant needs.

3. EXPLAIN – Making sense of the experiences

AIM: Students can calculate above- and below-ground carbon stocks in tree biomass and carbon sequestration by trees.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- Which habitat/area had the highest biomass? Why?
- What happens if humans use wetland forests for agriculture, forestry, hiking, or settlements?

TEACHER SUPPORT: This activity aims to enable students to calculate both above- and below-ground carbon stocks in tree biomass and understand the role of trees in carbon sequestration. By analyzing data collected during their field trip, students will explore which habitats have the highest biomass and discuss the impacts of human activities on these vital ecosystems.

MATERIALS NEEDED: worksheet for carbon calculation, calculator

ACTIVITY OVERVIEW

- 1 The teacher hands out the worksheet “How to calculate CO₂-sequestration”
- 2 Ensure students have their field trip notes ready, containing the data they collected.
- 3 After completing the calculations, compare the results.
- 4 Facilitate a discussion on the potential consequences of converting wetlands into arable land, settlements, or using them for forestry or tourism. Highlight how the first two transformations can lead to the loss of carbon sequestration potential, while the latter two uses can help maintain it.

4. EXTEND / ELABORATE – Expanding understanding

AIM: Students can name large natural and human CO₂ emitters and explain how CO₂ emissions can be reduced globally and by each of them.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- Which natural and human CO₂ sources can you find? What are the largest CO₂ emitters?
- How can CO₂ emissions be compensated/reduced globally and by yourself?

TEACHER SUPPORT:

- This activity aims to help students identify significant natural and human sources of CO₂ emissions and explore strategies for reducing these emissions both globally and individually.
- By investigating various sectors and calculating their own carbon footprints, students will gain insight into the impact of human activities on climate change and the importance of sustainable practices.

MATERIALS NEEDED: Computer, smartphone

ACTIVITY OVERVIEW

- 1 Students calculate their CO₂ footprint
- 2 Students search for further CO₂ emission data of different economic sectors (transport, industry, farming, households, etc)
- 3 Students discuss ways to reduce CO₂ emissions in general and at home
- 4 Based on the findings in the field, how many (floodplain) forests have to be restored to compensate for the global human CO₂ emissions?

Background information and links:

Carbon Footprint Calculator – CO₂ Emissions

- Link: <https://www.carbonfootprint.com/calculator.aspx>
- The calculator helps individuals and organizations estimate their carbon footprint and CO₂ emissions based on various activities, such as energy consumption, transportation, waste generation, etc. Based on the data entered, the calculator provides an estimate of the total CO₂ emissions produced and may suggest strategies for reducing those emissions.

CDP – Carbon Disclosure Project

- Link: <https://www.cdp.net/en>
- CDP is a nonprofit organization that encourages companies and cities to disclose their environmental and climate data. Many international companies participate in CDP surveys annually, providing detailed information on their CO₂ emissions and climate strategies.

Global Reporting Initiative (GRI)

- Link: <https://www.globalreporting.org/>
- GRI is one of the leading global organizations for sustainability reporting. It provides standards that help companies disclose their environmental, social, and governance (ESG) data. Many companies publish their CO₂ emissions in GRI-compliant sustainability reports.

IEA (International Energy Agency) – CO₂ Emissions Data

- Link: <https://www.iea.org/>
- The IEA provides extensive data on CO₂ emissions at both the global and regional levels, including information related to energy production and emissions from large industries and companies.

5. EVALUATE – Testing knowledge through games

AIM: Assess students' understanding of the emission and sequestration of carbon and the role of (wetland) forests as a carbon sink.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- Can the students draw connections between global warming, CO₂ emissions, carbon sequestration, and the importance of intact (wetland) forests?

TEACHER SUPPORT: This activity assesses students' understanding of carbon emission and sequestration, and the crucial role of wetland forests as carbon sinks. Through a climate game, students will explore connections between global warming, CO₂ emissions, carbon sequestration, and the importance of preserving intact wetland forests.

ACTIVITY: PLAY A CLIMATE GAME - GAME SUGGESTIONS:

- **„CLIMATE CALL GAME“**
Students learn how everyday activities impact the climate by playing the game. The game is engaging and informative, leading to lively discussions and eye-opening discoveries.
2-6 players, one round takes about 15 minutes, age 12+; <https://climatecallgame.com/>
- **“CLIMATE CHANGE: THE GAME” (2023)**
Players simulate decisions related to policy, economics, and technology to reduce emissions and combat climate change. While CO₂ certificates are not explicitly traded, the game explores emissions reductions and the global efforts to tackle climate change.
2-5 players, 60-120 min, age 12+;
<https://boardgamegeek.com/boardgame/390899/climate-change-the-game>
- **„CO₂ – SECOND CHANCE“ (2018)**
This game revolves around the global CO₂ emission market and the challenge of promoting renewable energy while trading CO₂ certificates. Players take on the role of companies that need to reduce their CO₂ emissions to earn CO₂ certificates, which can then be traded with other companies.
1-4 players, 60-120 min, age 12+;
<https://boardgamegeek.com/boardgame/214887/co2-second-chance>
- **“POWER GRID” (2004)**
In this game, players build an energy network and trade energy sources, some of which cause CO₂ emissions. While not directly focused on CO₂ certificates, it deals with sustainable energy and the challenges of the energy market.
2-6 players, 120 min, age: 12+;
<https://boardgamegeek.com/boardgame/2651/power-grid>

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CARBON SEQUESTRATION

WORKSHEET “ENGAGE - CLIMATE CHANGE EXPERIMENT”

MATERIALS NEEDED:

- Three 200-250 mL glass bottles with an airtight lid (e.g., preserving bottles),
- limestone (CaCO_3) powder,
- sponge,
- weak acid or descaling solution,
- three infrared lamps,
- three small thermometers (should fit into the glass bottles),
- stopwatch

INSTRUCTIONS:

- 1 Place the bottles in a row with approx. 1 m distance from each other. Install the infrared lamps 10-20 cm behind each bottle. All bottles must be completely dry before you start the experiment.
- 2 Place the thermometers inside the bottles.
- 3 Close one bottle airtight (reference bottle).
- 4 Wet the sponge, place it in the second bottle, and close the bottle airtight (water vapor bottle)
- 5 Fill the limestone powder into the third bottle, add a small amount of descaling solution, and close it airtight. You will see bubbles on the limestone indicating CO_2 release (CO_2 bottle).
- 5 Record the start temperature and time. Then turn on the infrared lamps and record the temperature every minute.

MEASUREMENT TABLE

Reference Bottle

Water Vapor Bottle

CO₂ Bottle

Time	Temp.	Time	Temp.	Time	Temp.

RESULTS AND EXPLANATION:

CARBON SEQUESTRATION

WORKSHEET EXPLORE – TREE BIOMASS

ESTIMATION OF ABOVE-GROUND AND BELOW-GROUND ORGANIC CARBON THROUGH TREE BIOMASS MEASUREMENT

MATERIALS NEEDED:

Flexible 2 m tape; 20-30 m long tape (if possible); stick of approximately an arm's length; smartphone; tree biomass form

OUTDOOR:

Your teacher has pre-selected a survey area and specific sites within this area to facilitate your measurements. These selections include representative and varied habitats and were chosen for their manageable tree density and accessibility, making height estimation easier. For each site, proceed as follows:

1. Take a picture of the site and note the **GPS data, the date, and time of the survey** in the "Tree biomass form".
2. **Measure** the circumference of each tree within this site via the "Diameter-at-Breast-Height method" (see measurement instructions)
3. Identify each tree species using the App "Flora incognita". Note the species' names and the circumferences in the "Tree biomass form".
4. **Choose 2 to 3 trees that show the average height at the site.** Use the "Triangle Method" to estimate their height (see measurement instructions).
5. Add **indicator values** for each species using the Flora incognita App: Go to the species description and scroll down to "treat". Depending on the species, you can find information on the type of pollination, leaf endurance, toxicity, protection value, and indicator values for nutrients (nitrate), moisture, light, temperature, soil reaction (pH), and salinity. The indicators provide information about the ecological requirements of the species. The higher the value, the more the plant needs.
6. With the height and circumference, you can now estimate the tree's biomass and carbon storage (see worksheet "calculation carbon sequestration").

MEASUREMENT INSTRUCTIONS

“DIAMETER-AT-BREAST-HEIGHT” METHOD TO DETERMINE THE CIRCUMFERENCE OF A TREE

1. Determine the Measurement Height at 1.37 m. A height of 1.37 meters represents the mean tree diameter. If the tree is on a slope, take the measurement from the mid-point between the uphill and downhill sides of the base.
2. Wrap the measuring tape tightly around the tree trunk at the 1.37-meter height. Record the circumference in centimeters in your protocol.
3. Use your smartphone and the app *Flora Incognita* to identify the tree species. Record the identified species in your protocol.

Figure 1:
diameter-at-breast-height measurement

“TRIANGLE METHOD” TO DETERMINE THE TREE HEIGHT

1. Choose a tree that you can see entirely from base to top. Ensure that the surrounding terrain is level.
2. Find a straight stick that is as long as your outstretched arm (from shoulder to fingertips).
3. Hold the stick with your outstretched arm in a vertical position so that a right-angled triangle is formed between your arm and the stick. Stand facing the tree and slowly walk backward in a straight line. Stop when the bottom of the stick lines up with the base of the tree, and the top of the stick lines up with the top of the tree.
4. Mark your position on the ground and measure the distance from this spot to the base of the tree. You can measure this distance either with a long measuring tape (20-30 m) or by pacing the distance between this spot and the tree using long steps (roughly 1 meter per step).
5. The distance measured corresponds to the height of the tree. Write it down in your protocol (tree biomass form).
6. Repeat the procedure for two more trees.

Figure 2:
position for triangle method

Figure 3:
triangle method measurement

CARBON SEQUESTRATION

WORKSHEET EXPLAIN - HOW TO CALCULATE CO₂-SEQUESTRATION

1 Have your field trip notes ready, containing the data on tree circumferences and heights that you collected.

2 Calculate the **mean tree radius** by dividing the measured circumference by $2 \times \pi$. π is 3.14.

$$\text{TREE RADIUS } r \text{ (cm)} = \text{TREE CIRCUMFERENCE (cm)} / (2 \times 3.14)$$

3 Pay attention to the units! If you have measured the circumference in centimeters, you need to **convert the radius to meters** for the following formulas. Divide the radius by 100 (100 cm is 1 m).

$$r \text{ (cm)} / 100 = r \text{ (m)}$$

4 Calculate the **trunk volume** via the tree height h (m) and the radius r (m) using the following formula:

$$\text{TRUNK VOLUME TV (m}^3\text{)} = 3.14 \times r^2 \times h$$

5 Estimate the entire **tree volume** V by multiplying the trunk volume by the factor 1.4. This factor accounts for the root and canopy biomass (see picture).

$$V \text{ (m}^3\text{)} = \text{TV} \times 1.4$$

- 6 For the total organic carbon content TC stored in the tree, multiply the tree volume V (m³) by the wood density D (kg/m³) and the organic carbon content of wood. The density of dry wood depends on the tree species (see list below). For a rough estimation, take a mean of 530 kg/m³. The carbon content of wood is 50% of the dry mass.

$$\text{TOTAL CARBON CONTENT TC (kg)} = \text{TOTAL VOLUME} \times \text{DENSITY} \times 0.5$$

- 7 Calculate the amount of CO₂ sequestered by the tree by multiplying the total carbon content TC (kg) by 3.67. This factor is derived from the weight ratio of CO₂ to C, which is 44/12 = 3.67.

$$\text{CO}_2 \text{ SEQUESTERED (kg)} = \text{TC} \times 3.67$$

- 8 **IMPORTANT:** This value represents the CO₂ sequestered in the entire lifetime of the tree. To ascertain the annual CO₂ sequestration rate, divide the total CO₂ sequestered by the tree's age (if available).

WOOD DENSITIES FOR COMMON TREES

Table 5.6 Stem wood densities per tree species that were used to calculate carbon pools in trees

Tree species Group	Included tree species	Wood density (kg m ⁻³)
Salix	Salix alba, Salix caprea, Salix cinerea, Salix eleagnos, Salix fragilis, Salix sp.	330
Thuja	Thuja sp.	350
Cedrus	Cedrus atlantica, Cedrus deodara	400
Abies/Populus	Abies alba, Abies borisii-regis, Abies cephalonica, Abies grandis, Abies nordmanniana, Abies pinsapo, Abies procera, Pinus radiata, Pinus strobus, Populus alba, Populus canescens, Populus hybridus, Populus nigra, Populus tremula.	410
Picea	Picea abies, Picea omorika	400
Picea sitchensis	Picea sitchensis	350
Tsuga	Tsuga sp.	440
Other conifers	Cupressus lusitanica, Cupressus sempervirens, Juniperus communis, Juniperus oxycedrus, Juniperus phoenicea, Juniperus sabina, Juniperus thurifera, Taxus baccata, Chamaecyparis lawsoniana, Other conifers	450 ¹
Pseudotsuga	Pseudotsuga menziesii	470
Pinus/Tilia	Pinus brutia, Pinus canariensis, Pinus cembra, Pinus contorta, Pinus halepensis, Pinus heldreichii, Pinus leucodermis, Pinus mugo, Pinus nigra, Pinus pinaster, Pinus pinea, Pinus sylvestris, Pinus uncinata, Tilia cordata, Tilia platyphyllos.	490
Alnus	Alnus cordata, Alnus glutinosa, Alnus incana, Alnus viridis	510
Prunus/Larix	Prunus avium, Prunus dulcis, Prunus padus, Prunus serotina, Larix decidua, Larix kaempferi	550
Juglans	Juglans nigra, Juglans regia	560
Olea/Platanus	Olea europaea, Platanus orientalis	580
Acer	Acer campestre, Acer monspessulanum, Acer opalus, Acer platanoides, Castanea sativa	590
Other broadleaves	Buxus sempervirens, Ilex aquifolium, Tamarix africana, Arbutus unedo, Arbutus andrachne, Ceratonia siliqua, Cercis siliquastrum, Erica arborea, Erica scoparia, Erica manipuliflora, Phillyrea latifolia, Phillyrea angustifolia, Pistacia lentiscus, Pistacia terebinthus, Rhamnus oleoides, Rhamnus alaternus, Betula tortuosa, Ceratonia siliqua (same as 75), Crataegus monogyna, Other broadleaves	595 ¹
Betula	Betula pendula, Betula pubescens	610
Acer/Ulmus	Acer pseudoplatanus, Ulmus glabra, Ulmus laevis, Ulmus minor	640
Fraxinus/Quercus	Fraxinus angustifolia, Fraxinus excelsior, Fraxinus ornus, Quercus cerris, Quercus coccifera, Quercus faginea, Quercus frainetto, Quercus fruticosa, Quercus ilex, Quercus macrolepis, Quercus petraea, Quercus pubescens, Quercus pyrenaica, Quercus robur, Quercus rotundifolia, Quercus rubra, Quercus suber, Quercus trojana	600
Fagus	Fagus moesiaca, Fagus orientalis, Fagus sylvatica	680
Eucalyptus	Eucalyptus sp., Malus domestica, Pyrus communis, Laurus nobilis, Myrtus communis	700
Sorbus	Sorbus aria, Sorbus aucuparia, Sorbus domestica, Sorbus torminalis	730
Robinia pseudacacia	Robinia pseudacacia	740
Carpinus	Carpinus betulus, Carpinus orientalis, Corylus avellana, Ostrya carpinifolia	790

¹ Stem densities for the considered other conifers and other broadleaves have been set at the average of all species

From: EC - UN/ECE, 2003; W. de Vries, G.J. Reinds, M. Posch, M. J. Sanz, G.H.M. Krause, V. Calatayud, J.P. Renaud, J.L. Dupouey, H. Sterba, E.M. Vel, M. Dobbertin, P. Gundersen and J.C.H. Voogd. Intensive Monitoring of Forest Ecosystems in Europe, 2003 Technical Report. EC, UN/ECE 2003, Brussels, Geneva, 163 pp.